

Kulbhushan Jadhav Case: A Mystery of a Win-Win Situation for Pakistan and India

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: September 26, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: April 28, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Security, Espionage, Terrorist activity, International Law, Diplomacy</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6503730</p>	<p><i>Kulbhushan Jadhav, an Indian national, was detained on terrorist and espionage accusations in Pakistan's Baluchistan province. Jadhav was allegedly kidnapped from Iran by Pakistani security forces, according to the Indian foreign ministry. Kulbhushan was an Indian Navy officer, according to Pakistan's version. Kulbhushan, on the other hand, was an ex-Naval officer who resigned in 2001, according to the Indian account. This article will present a proper perspective on the role of international law in general, as well as its importance in defining state-to-state relationships. It will also address the various approaches to reducing the influence of espionage in a country's foreign policy direction.</i></p>

Introduction

It is not commonplace for hostile intelligence agencies to use neighbouring soils as launch pads for disruptive and subversive operations. The most important question is if the government of the neighbouring country is aware of it. India has been utilizing Iranian and Afghan territory for this purpose in Pakistan. Successive Afghan administrations were aware of this activity, and at times, they were a willing participant in some Indian intelligence operations. An event in connection to the above arose many speculations in terms of espionage as a means of the disruptive process by India in Pakistan. KulbushanJadhav was a commando in the Indian Navy who was involved in subversive activities inside Pakistan at the behest of Indian intelligence agency 'Raw,' according to the Pakistani authorities. On the 3rd of May 2016, he was apprehended in Baluchistan during a counter-intelligence operation. The Indian authorities acknowledged Jadhav as a former naval officer but denied any current ties to him, claiming that he retired prematurely and was kidnapped in Iran's Chabahar area. In any case, no reasonable explanation for his later transit to Pakistan was presented. On the 10th of April, 2017, a Pakistani Field Marshal General condemned Jadhav to death. The International Court of Justice (ICJ) postponed the execution pending the case's final verdict in response to India's request for interim remedies. The International Court of Justice (ICJ) issued its final ruling in the Kulbushan Jadhav dispute between India and Pakistan on the 17th of July, 2019. The court concluded that Pakistan had violated its responsibilities under the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations, 1963 (hereinafter VCCR) to give consular access to a person from a party state, with a 15-1 majority finding. As a result, the court ordered Pakistan to stop Jadhav's execution and examine his whole trial and conviction process, as well as provide India consular access. At the same time, the court negated the request of India to free Jadhav and give assurance of his safe return to India. Although this ruling might be considered a success for one state and a defeat for the other, it can also be viewed as a win-win situation because international law ultimately triumphed. Counter-terrorism and espionage regulations, for example, were determined to be subordinate to the international law of consular relations in this ruling. Similarly, providing consular access was recognized as an essential aspect of the fair trial process by the international community. Likewise, the ICJ's reluctance to approve of India's demand to set Jadhav free and assure his safe transit to India bolstered the UN Charter's norm of non-intervention in domestic affairs. In addition to the preceding, Pakistan's execution of the judgment established its adherence to international law. Unlike Israel, which refused to honour the Advisory Opinion of the International Court of Justice (2004) in the construction of the 'wall case', Pakistan not only carried out the order to provide consular access but also passed legislation to allow civilian courts to review the military court's order if it violated international law.

Obedience to the Moralities of international law and its connection with the Proceedings of ICJ.

Disputes arising from the interpretation or application of the Convention are subject to the compulsory jurisdiction of the International Court of Justice (ICJ), and any party to the present protocol may bring a case before the court. The International Court of Justice statute provides that the court has jurisdiction over all

subjects presented to it by the parties and all issues covered by the UN Charter or existing treaties or conventions. In April 2017, a Pakistani military court sentenced Indian national Kulbhushan Jadhav to death. On the 8th of May, 2017, India submitted a request to commence proceedings against Pakistan in connection with a dispute over alleged violations of the (VCCR) of the 24th of April, 1963, in the case of Mr Kulbhushan Jadhav, an Indian native. According to India, Pakistan allegedly failed to notify India "soon" about the arrest and custody of one of its citizens. Jadhav had not been informed of his rights under article 36 of the (VCCR), and India's consular officer had been denied access to Mr Jadhav. At the same time, he was detained, detained, and imprisoned, and was unable to chat, correspond, or arrange for his legal representation while detained, detained, and imprisoned. India's application stated that the court's jurisdiction is based on Article 36, paragraph 1 of the ICJ statute and article 1 of the optional protocol (VCCR). On the same day, India filed a motion for preliminary injunctions, asking the court to order Pakistan to take all necessary steps to prevent Kulbhushan's execution and to guarantee that no action is taken that would jeopardize his life as well as India's or Mr Kulbhushan's rights if the case goes to trial. The court ordered Pakistan to "take all means at its disposal to ensure that Mr Jadhav is not executed pending a final resolution in the case, and to inform the court of any measures taken in compliance with the order" in an order dated the 18th of May 2017. It also decided not to act until the court rendered a final decision. A public hearing on the facts of the case was held from the 18th to the 21st of February 2019. The honourable court described the background of the matter in its the 17th of July 2019 judgement before concluding that it has jurisdiction to hear India's claim based on alleged violations of the Vienna Convention. Pakistan's three advisability arguments, which were based on India's alleged misuse of the process, abuses of human rights, and illegal behaviour, were next addressed by the court. The court decided that the wisest course of action was to apply in India. Regarding the case's merits, the court looks at each of Pakistan's three justifications for the Vienna Convention's applicability one by one. The court determined that the Vienna Convention applied in this instance after deciding that none of Pakistan's claims could be established, regardless of whether. Kulbhushan Jadhav was involved in espionage activities.

Effect of Geo-Strategic Alignment between Pakistan -China and Espionage by India, a Reality or a Misnomer.

Following his detention, Kulbhushan Yadav recorded a confessional video in which he acknowledged being an Indian Naval officer who was dispatched to Pakistan to cause trouble through terrorism. One of his alleged main goals was to destroy the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) project by providing naval warfare training to Baloch separatists for them to assault the seaports of Gwadar and Karachi.

India filed a case with the International Court of Justice (ICJ) shortly after, stating that Pakistan had breached the Vienna Convention on Consular Relations of 1963. India asserted the ICJ's jurisdiction under Article 36(1) of the ICJ statute and article 1 of the VCCR optional protocol. According to the statute, the court has jurisdiction over all problems raised by the parties, as well as any topics covered by the UN Charter, treaties, or conventions in force. Article I of the optional protocol, states that any disagreement over the Convention's implementation or interpretation is subject to mandatory ICJ jurisdiction, and any party to the dispute who is also a party to the protocol can bring the case to the court. In response to Pakistan's claims that India had misused the court's procedure, the ICJ issued interim measures in April 2017, ordering Pakistan to halt the execution of Kulbhushan Yadav until the case was finally decided on the merits by the ICJ. Before this, a Pakistani military court found Kulbhushan guilty of terrorism and espionage and sentenced him to death. India retaliated by accusing Pakistan of violating the (VCCR) 1963's significant responsibilities. For example, India claimed that the Convention required Pakistan to "inform without delay." The sending state was notified that one of its citizens had been detained, whereas India was reported three weeks after the arrest/trial. India further claimed that Pakistan failed to inform the accused Yadav of his right to interact with the sending state's counsellor and to have sufficient legal representation. Finally, India claims that the sending state's counsellor was denied access to Kulbhushan Yadav while he was detained. All of Pakistan's actions defied the 1967 Vienna counsellor convention.

The Drop Scene of the Episode through the Preliminary Judgment.

According to the world court, Pakistan violated its international commitments by denying Jadhav's rights under Article 36. Furthermore, Pakistan failed to notify India about the arrest and custody of a Pakistani national, even though the arrest was reported to India three weeks later. Finally, the international court found that the Indian counsellor officer was denied access to Jadhav, denying individual rights such as counsellor communication with the detainee and legal counsel. Article 1 of the optional protocol allows these rights to be enforced. The ICJ further stated that India's inability to collaborate with Pakistan in the inquiry does not constitute a basis for denying counsellors access under Article 36 of (VCCR). Individual privileges provided under the above-stated article and article 1 of the optional protocol cannot be denied. As a result, Pakistan has been found to violate the Convention's Article 36 responsibilities. Invoking the restitution ad integrum, India requested that the military court's conviction be overturned or nullified, Jadhav is released, and his return to India be assisted to return the situation to its former state. The court decided that this could not be done but that

Pakistan should review or reassess its military court's decision to construct a plausible notion of the violation of article 36 of the (VCCR).

Further Proceedings through an Interim Application by India to Deviate From the Main Allegation of Espionage.

Furthermore, on the 8th of May, 2017, India applied to the International Court of Justice (ICJ), citing violations of the (VCCR) 1963 in the case of Mr Jadhav's trial and imprisonment. Pakistan voiced three concerns about the Indian application's suitability. To begin with, Pakistan maintained that India had abused the process and hence was not entitled to the remedies sought. Pakistan claimed that a constitutional right of compassion or freedom of appeal to the president is accessible within 150 days of conviction to establish the abuse of procedure. However, the execution was carried out instead of exercising this privilege, which would have delayed the death by 150 days. Meanwhile, India filed a petition in the same court for temporary measures. The court concluded that India did not commit any illegality or abuse of the process by approaching the court for provisional measures because the clemency procedure was not definite regarding the time within which the petition must be decided and whether the execution will be executed or suspended as a result of the petition. The court went on to say in its judgment that the clemency petition's procedure and outcome were both unclear and so unreliable. Second, Pakistan maintained that India had abused the process because it could have used alternative dispute resolution options, such as arbitration and conciliation, as allowed under the optional protocol. The court responded that the optional protocol's articles II and III provisions are not intended to usurp. Under article 36, seize the courts' unambiguous jurisdiction (1). These provisions can only be used if the parties agree not to have their issues resolved by the International Court of Justice. As a result, India cannot be accused of abusing the process by refusing to use arbitration and conciliation. As has been the case in many previous situations, a country must first make a clear cut case to challenge visibility based on procedural violations. Pakistan submitted a variety of challenges to India's application's admissibility. To begin with, Pakistan claimed that India did not participate in the criminal investigation against Jadhav and that Pakistan's demands for cooperation fell on deaf ears. According to the court, the performance of an obligation under article 36(1) is not restricted to the sending state fulfilling any requirement. India also stated that there is no Mutual Legal Assistance Treaty between India and Pakistan that would provide a basis for cooperation in criminal investigations. As a result, the court dismissed this objection. Additionally, Pakistan claimed that India failed to provide original documentation regarding Jadhav's nationality despite issuing an original passport with a cover name. According to the ICJ, Pakistan has repeatedly referred to him as an Indian citizen. India has filed a request to preserve his rights; therefore, Jadhav's nationality is no doubt. Another concern registered by Pakistan was that India had breached its international responsibilities, specifically SCR 1373 (2001), by refusing to cooperate in an inquiry into Jadhav's anti-terrorist activities. The international court overruled this challenge by stating that the seeking state's commitment under article 36(1) (VCCR) is not conditioned on the requesting state's submission to other international obligations. Lastly, in addition to her concerns, Pakistan claimed that India had some ulterior motive behind knowing the door of ICJ because it provided an original passport to disguise its identity. Hence, it is not entitled to relief. The international court concluded that the clean hands doctrine may only be used as a cause for refusing admissibility if it can show how the illegality prevents the party in compliance from completing its duties. If Pakistan relies on this concept, it must explain how India's illegal action hindered it from carrying out its Article 36 obligations. This was used in the case of the Danube Dam, as on the 16th of September, 1977, The Hungarian People's Republic and the Czechoslovak People's Republic agreed to develop and operate the Gabckovo-Nagymaros lock system to maximize the use of the Danube's natural resources between Bratislava and Budapest. However, this case is not as severe as the Kulbhushan Jadhav's one because many instances are scrutinized, including the most significant one, i.e, espionage. In the context of Pakistan's concerns to its last point, Pakistan used the ex-injuria principle, which states that illegal behaviour cannot change the law amongst conflicting parties. This approach is inapplicable in the circumstances of this case; the court quantified.

An overview of the matters in dispute: (Crux of the Judgment)

In this case, India filed a complaint with ICJ against Pakistan for violating its treaty duties (VCCR). Pakistan allegedly restricted Kulbhushan's rights under Article 36, according to India (VCCR). Including violation regarding informing Jadhav of his rights under Article 36, also Pakistan did not promptly notify India, a treaty partner, of the arrest of a national, and lastly, denying Jadhav access to a counsellor in submission with article 36 of the VCCR, which states that a counsellor should have access to a detainee to communicate with him and give legal representation. ICJ accepted India's three arguments and found Pakistan in violation of Article 36 almost unanimously. According to the ICJ, both Pakistan and India are parties to the (VCCR) and its optional protocol, which establishes the ICJ's authority over disputes arising from the explanation and application of the (VCCR) 1963. Pakistan, in its defence, objected to the petition's admission and its applicability (VCCR). Pakistan raised the following objections to admissibility:

- i. Abuse of process: At the interim stage, India failed to inform the ICJ that the remedy of clemency was available under Pakistani law. The ICJ, on the other hand, found that the remedy was ambiguous because no time limit was set for the appeal/petition to be resolved.

ii. Abuse of rights: India might have used the optional protocol's Art II and III, which provide for arbitration and conciliation. In response, the ICJ ruled that the availability of these tools does not preclude a state from seeking the resolution of a dispute through the ICJ. The fact that these remedies are not available does not mean that the remedy is no longer available under Article I of the optional protocol.

iii. Pakistan also claimed that India's intentions are not clean because it did not cooperate with Pakistan in conducting the inquiry and acquiring evidence against Jadhav. India has disobeyed the terms of Security Council resolution 1373 of 2000. If India has broken international law, it cannot claim that other countries have broken it or that its rights have been denied.

Response of International Court of Justice and Pakistan's Objections against the Applicability of the Convention.

In response, the ICJ ruled that the rights provided by article 36 are not contingent on other governments fulfilling their international duties. If a national of a state party to the (VCCR) is discovered on the territory of another state party, the latter is required to offer consular rights under article 36 (VCCR), regardless of whether the sending state has met its international duties. In their individual views and declarations, some justices of the ICJ criticized the verdict for failing to refer to these rights as core human rights of fair trial and due process. Pakistan raised three concerns about the Convention's applicability. Firstly, Pakistan maintained that article 36 of (VCCR) is not appropriate to be applied to cases of terrorism and spying. Second, Pakistan asserted that in cases of spying, customary international law allows a state to waive consular access. In answer to the first two reasons, the ICJ found nowhere in the Convention's drafting history that *Travaux Préparatoires* stated that those suspected of terrorism or espionage might not be granted consular access. Article 36 is unconditional to provide these rights and makes no distinction between sorts of offences. Giving consular access is part of a fair trial. Several counter-terrorist accords adopted by states explicitly say that a person accused of terrorism shall be given access to his state's representative, and a fair trial should be granted. As a result, every national of a party state who finds himself on the territory of another party state has access to consular services. Finally, Pakistan demanded that the 2008 consular access agreement govern the consular contact between Pakistan and India rather than the bilateral arrangement (VCCR).

Court's Response and Indian Prayer.

The court remarked that if this were the parties' intent, it would have been plainly stated in the 2008 agreement. On the other hand, the agreement expressly states that it is intended to amplify, supplement, and enlarge the rights afforded by Article 36. (VCCR). As a result, all three admissibility challenges were dismissed.

Pakistan, on the other hand, was not without hope. India further requested that:

1. Jadhav's sentence and conviction by Pakistan's military court be overturned.
2. Jadhav should be released.
3. Jadhav's safe arrival in India must be guaranteed.

Alternatively, India argued that if Jadhav could not be let free, the execution of his sentence should be halted until the sentence and conviction of the Military Court's judgment are reviewed or reconsidered by a civilian court. Although the world court denied India's request to have the sentence and conviction overturned, it ordered Pakistan to examine and reconsider the sentence and conviction on the grounds that it was delivered in breach of Jadhav's international law rights under article 36. (VCCR). As a result, its review must be effective, and a civilian court must conduct the review. Pakistan may consider introducing legislation if it does not have a law that allows a civilian court to examine a military court's verdict based on a violation of international law. To this end, the total effect should be given that Jadhav's right under article 36 was infringed upon because India and RAW never apologized for this man's acts. They even disputed that he was apprehended in Pakistan's Balochistan province, claiming that he had been kidnapped in Iran. Finally, the court's reluctance to examine state espionage practices in depth is understandable, given that states have traditionally avoided litigating spying disagreements (for example, see *Timor-Leste v Australia*). The fact that none of the 177 states parties to the VCCR responded to the court's invitation under Article 63 of the Statute of the Court to express their views on whether Article 36 of the VCCR provides for a customary international law except in the case of espionage exemplifies this in the Jadhav proceedings.

Conclusion.

It may be argued that the decision was beneficial to both India and Pakistan. On the one hand, the (ICJ) highlighted Pakistan's violation of international law and rejected its explanation of espionage and terrorism. At the same time, the ICJ refrained from interfering in Pakistan's internal affairs. Despite the Indian appeal, it did not overturn the military court's decision, instead requesting a review because the trial was compromised by a failure to give consular access (which had implications for the accused's fair trial rights). Pakistan has done well to accept the judgment; it shows we are a responsible state. The ICJ has no enforcement mechanism, and like Israel, Pakistan too could have refused to honour its judgment, but we accepted it wholeheartedly. Since the verdict was delivered, Jadhav had been provided consular access for two hours. Even his wife and mother were allowed to meet him. Likewise, execution remains suspended, and a bill has been presented in the parliament to change the law whereby the civilian court can review the military court's decision based on violation of

international law. Pakistan has done well by accepting the verdict; it demonstrates that we are a responsible nation. The International Court of Justice has no enforcement mechanism, and Pakistan, like Israel, could have refused to obey its ruling, but we instead accepted it wholeheartedly. Since the sentence was handed down, Jadhav has been granted consular access for two hours. Even his wife and mother were allowed to meet him. Similarly, executions have been halted, and a bill has been introduced in parliament to alter the law so that a civilian court can review a military court's decision if it is in breach of international law. When news headlines are considered relevance optimizers, it is evident that news organizations in Pakistan and India are actively crafting a narrative that is not just driven by their sociopolitical agendas but also in line with their overall policy toward one another. To sway public opinion in India's favor, Indian newspapers have openly employed emotion-laced journalistic nationalism to appeal to public sympathy and, therefore, effectively sway public opinion on Pakistan's treatment of an Indian national. On the other hand, the Pakistani media takes a contradictory and ambiguous position, shifting from offensive to defensive, action-oriented to submissive. As the 'logical conclusion' of Jadhav's case approaches, it will be interesting to see how the respective countries' media frame the story.

Last but not least, to combat the aforementioned security concerns, comprehensive measures are required. Diplomatic rules should be convinced at the international level to stop India's ongoing involvement. Pakistan's security system, in a nutshell, has reached a breaking point. The ability to defend the nation's physical integrity and territory, maintain reasonable economic connections with the rest of the world, protect the nation's nature, institutions, and government from outside disruption, and control its borders is characterized as national security.

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